

UNPACKING READING CHALLENGES IN ELEMENTARY LEVEL: A MULTIPLE CASE STUDY

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Unpacking Reading Challenges in Elementary Level: A Multiple Case Study

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Abstract

This multiple case study aimed to accumulate and understand the experiences of elementary teachers in handling students with reading challenges. Using purposive sampling and inclusion criteria, the participating four (4) elementary teachers were identified. Through in-depth interviews, observations, and field notes, comprehensive data were gathered. Thematic analysis and cross-case analysis were utilized, revealing that addressing reading challenges are highly beneficial, contributing to their personal and professional growth. Despite challenges, elementary teachers strived and find motivation through the support from their colleagues, fostering a positive outlook, and employing strategies for academic success and personal development. Realizations about the the reading challenges among students, their role for academic success, and their motivation to help students were key drivers for participation.

Keywords: *reading comprehension, elementary teachers, multiple case study, Philippines*

Introduction

Reading is indeed one of the most important macro skills that should be developed among learners to become successful in their literacy and academic endeavours. However, the pandemic has greatly impacted student's learning showing distinct changes in the growth of basic reading skills during different time periods over the past year. The results of a nationwide reading assessment conducted among students in first to fourth grades indicate a significant slowdown in the progression of their oral reading fluency, which pertains to their capacity to read aloud with speed and precision. This deceleration was predominantly observed in the spring of 2020, coinciding with the sudden school closures resulting from the COVID-19 pandemic. Following the start of the COVID-19 school closings, children did not improve their reading fluency over the following five months. Moreover, the relative losses, though, are substantial, students have dropped roughly a third of a year behind where they should be in terms of reading development (Stanford, 2021).

In a global context, especially in Pakistan, reading proficiency has emerged as a significant concern. The acquisition of English reading skills is proving to be a formidable challenge for students, and a significant number of them face difficulty in effectively reading their textbooks. Students encounter multiple challenges when it comes to reading English and they show low proficiency in this skill. Several issues have been identified, including a limited knowledge of vocabulary, poor reading habits, and a general lack of interest in the reading comprehension course. Furthermore, English has been made a mandatory subject in Pakistan, spanning from primary to graduation levels. However, many students are reluctant to engage with it due to their insufficient knowledge. It's worth noting that the medium of instruction in Pakistan is English, but unfortunately, many learners struggle with reading it effectively (Nurjanah, 2018; Shakil, 2020).

In the Philippines, particularly in Mindanao State University-Integrated Laboratory School, reading proficiency is seen to be the problem among the learners. Many students encounter difficulties when reading words, with a significant number expressing that they struggle to comprehend the content within the modules. Moreover, according to the 2019 PISA (Programme for International Student Assessment) data, Filipino students performed below the global average in reading comprehension. This implied that the Philippine educational system faces the challenge of fostering proficient readers. This suggests that there is a need to address the obstacles and possible areas for improvement in the reading ability of Filipino kids (Marohombsar, 2021).

The study has social relevance because the level of reading proficiency is one of the important aspects that each elementary students must be successful at and because it addresses critical educational and societal issues, from equity in education to long-term economic and community well-being. Its findings and implications can inform policies, practices, and community actions aimed at improving literacy and educational outcomes. On the other hand, the study is deemed urgent since low level of reading proficiency may lead to problems and complications in the quality of learning experiences of elementary learners. Poor level of reading proficiency may massively affect the learners academically and personally. Therefore, there is a need to address reading challenges at an early stage to ensure students' academic success as it enhance national competitiveness, and provide evidence-based methods for enhancing reading instructions in elementary level.

In my literature review, I have found related studies such as the study of Zanlorenzi et. al. (2023) entitled, "The Reading Challenges of Low Vision Students in Elementary School"; the "English Reading Proficiency and Academic Performance among Lower Primary School Children in Ghana" by Nyarko et. al. (2018); and the study of Durda et. al. (2020) entitled, "Proficiency Level Descriptors for Low Reading Proficiency: An Integrative Process Model". None of these studies were similar to this study as this focuses more on the time after pandemic, utilizing a multiple case study approach that allows for in-depth exploration, comparison and uncovering unique insights of diverse cases within a single study to measure the level of reading proficiency and experiences of elementary students which is still less explored in the body of knowledge. These premises prompted me to propose this study.

Furthermore, this work will be shared at research conferences and will be published in reputable research journals both nationally and internationally through relevant agencies to create a lively exchange among scholars and government authorities, promoting the sharing of research discoveries. The dissemination plan is thoughtfully designed to ensure that the research reaches a broad audience, thereby maximizing its impact. This includes targeted sharing with educational institutions and agencies that can directly benefit from the findings, such as school administrators, reading coordinators, and policymakers. By engaging these key stakeholders, the study aims to contribute to more effective reading programs and policies that support students with reading difficulties, ultimately leading to improved literacy outcomes in elementary education.

Research Questions

The main objective of this qualitative multiple case study was to explore and determine the perspectives of elementary teachers in dealing students with reading challenges. To achieve this objective, the study sought to answer the following research questions:

1. What are the unique characteristics of each case of elementary teachers?
2. What are the perceived challenges of each case of elementary teachers in terms of reading?
3. What are the ways of coping of each case of elementary teachers in their perceived challenges in elementary reading?
4. What are the insights of each case of elementary teachers in their perceived challenges in elementary reading?

Literature Review

Difficulty in Dealing with Non-readers

Individuals who struggle with their fluent reading abilities have some difficulty when reading a text. It has been tracked that students with reading difficulties generally have some issues, such as having short-term memory problems, being unable to maintain their attention, being emotionally weak, reading without thinking, a lack of eye-motor coordination, and reading the words backwards (Gedik & Akyol, 2022). However, Adapon and Mangila (2020) stated that the Department of Education- Zamboanga del Sur Division launched the Care for the Non-Readers (CNR) Program, the goal of this division-wide reading activity, featuring beginning and developmental reading, is to give children and learners who fall behind in reading the chance to catch up with the help of specialized one-on-one reading instruction from a reading teacher.

Limited Resources

School districts around the world are trying to find enough money to spend on resources in their classrooms. High-poverty communities are often the ones where schools are struggling the hardest. However, people who live close to the school pay less in school taxes. Additionally, schools in low-income communities are straining to obtain resources that results to students are affected in various ways by a lack of resources that indicates that they are not making the most of their education (Maffea, 2020).

Diverse Learning Needs

Related study emphasized the importance to focus on the needs of particular groups of students (such as low achievers or those with troublesome behaviors) because if not it, will fail to demonstrate how vulnerable and exposed students can become in difficult teaching and learning situations. Managing diversity in classrooms takes into account all students' needs, not to those with special education needs. Additionally, it suggested a skilled teacher's full involvement with children in the classroom. However, it is believed that behavior management in general is one of the largest obstacles for new teachers, but it was being showed that the benefits of out-of-field instruction on enhanced teachers' confidence, particularly on their ability to properly manage the classroom, and to quickly determine each student's particular learning needs and preferences (Plessis, 2018).

Effective Reading Strategy

In the previous study conducted, it stated the importance of employing reading strategies, as it has a significant influence on children's reading comprehension ability. Students have revealed that skimming, scanning, making predictions and questioning strategies been beneficial to students' reading comprehension. The students have a good attitude toward these methods as they were instructed or guided in the application of various reading methodologies so that they would understand how to use such strategies for successful grasp of academic materials. Hence, teachers will necessitate the ability to teach reading strategies that will aid pupils in comprehending and applying right ways to become good readers (Banditvilai, 2020).

Assessment and Monitoring

Progress monitoring entails the frequent (weekly, biweekly, or monthly) collecting of educational data in order to make judgments and decisions about instruction or the need for extra instructional support. The major goal of collecting data with progress monitoring measures is to evaluate student progression in important curricular areas (for example, reading, mathematics, and writing) or to examine specific sub-skills that contribute to student accomplishment in these areas. Additionally, many measures, such as Star Reading, aimsweb, and Dynamic Indicators of Basic Early Literacy Skills (DIBELS), have been established to track student growth in response to instruction or academic intervention (Bulut & Cormier, 2018).

Importance of Early Intervention

Related study stressed that reading intervention program aims to improve children's phonological awareness skills, develop their letter-knowledge, promote print and book awareness, and increase literacy engagement. The intervention lasts 12 weeks in kindergarten and that it is presented by the teachers in the classroom. Furthermore, the intervention combines direct instruction with a pedagogical approach based on playful learning. It employed multimodal strategies that promote the development of children's early reading skills in a structured and methodical manner, immersed in language-rich and meaning-oriented activities (Pascale et al., 2020).

Individualized Reading Instruction

The growing body of evidence indicates that personalized instruction, which is guided by assessments and tailored to the unique skills and capabilities of each student, proves to be more effective than generic, one-size-fits-all methods. This study aims to explore the utilization of language, decoding, and comprehension assessments to create customized literacy teaching strategies for students from kindergarten to third grade (Connor, 2018).

Methodology

Research Design

This study adopted a qualitative research design, utilizing a multiple case study approach. As noted by Rashid et. al. (2019), qualitative case studies offer a descriptive analysis of specific events within particular contexts. The design employed systematic methods to gather information about the phenomenon, primarily through interviews and dialogues. This approach aided in understanding the participants' experiences, perspectives, and challenges.

The multiple case qualitative design was used to gain insights into elementary teachers' perspectives on the reading challenges their students face. Through interviews, the researcher collected data on the experiences, challenges, and insights of the participants. The study explored the individual cases to understand the unique circumstances and statements provided by the informants.

Participants

The primary participants in this study were carefully chosen to provide rich and valuable data in understanding the research problem and central phenomenon. The researcher purposely selected four (4) Elementary Teachers who provided perspectives on the reading challenges faced by elementary learners. Overall, there were two (2) main participants and two (2) informants in this study. In accordance with Creswell (2014) which emphasized that case study is particularly suitable when the research problem involves developing an in-depth understanding of a "case" or bounded system. Creswell highlighted that case studies are most appropriate when the purpose is to understand a specific event, activity, process, or the experiences of one or more individuals within a defined context.

Procedure

The researcher adhered to a well-structured protocol throughout the study, covering every stage from pre-interview preparations to post-interview procedures. Initially, a set of interview guide questions was developed and then validated by a panel of experts. Afterward, the researcher secured an endorsement letter and obtained approval from the advisor to proceed with the study. Permission was then requested from the principal of Bunawan Elementary School and Napisulan Elementary School who provided a formal letter authorizing the researcher to conduct face-to-face interviews with elementary teachers.

After receiving the necessary approvals, the researcher obtained letters for the selected participants, formally requesting their consent to partake in the study. If the chosen participants agreed to participate, the researcher supplied them with a consent form for their signature. Subsequently, upon obtaining the approval letter from the validation panel, the researcher initiated the study. Prior to conducting the interviews, an orientation session was conducted by the researcher for all participants. During this session, the researcher elucidated the study's purpose, methodology, and the rights of the participants in the interview process. Additionally, permission to record the entire interview duration was sought from the participants. Following the interviews, the researcher took measures to safeguard the confidentiality of all recorded sessions. The recorded data was transcribed, and the resulting transcripts were subjected to verification by the participants. Upon completion of the verification process, the researcher proceeded to translate and analyze the data. The findings derived from this data analysis were then utilized to formulate conclusions and offer recommendations based on the study's outcome.

Data Analysis

The collected data from the in-depth interviews were transcribed, translated, and analyzed following Creswell's (2009) proposed process for data analysis. The researcher followed the steps recommended by Creswell. The responses of the participants, once translated, were systematically coded to facilitate a thematic analysis of the data within this case study. Thematic analysis, often referred to as coding, encompasses the process of categorizing responses and identifying recurring themes in the text to construct a structured representation of thematic concepts. These discernible themes offer valuable insights within the data, which can be further subjected to analysis and measurement.

Through the systematic process of thematic analysis, the researcher organized the dataset into themes or patterns. This enabled the researcher to identify and develop themes based on the obtained data, as described by Dye (2021). Throughout the data analysis phase, the researcher heavily depended on the transcripts and translated versions of the informants' responses. Employing a systematic coding process, the researcher categorized and structured the recurring responses to formulate an exhaustive thematic analysis. These concepts were methodically arranged and assessed, considering their interrelationships, commonalities, and distinctions, with the support of a data analyst.

Ethical Considerations

When collecting data from individuals, researchers follow ethical principles that guide their research design and procedures. The objectives of human research often include understanding real- world phenomena, finding effective treatments, studying behavior, and improving lives. Adhering to ethical guidelines is essential for maintaining academic and scientific integrity, enhancing the validity of research, and protecting participants' rights (Bhandari, 2022).

In this study, the researcher took deliberate steps to uphold ethical standards. Before conducting the interviews, an informed consent form was prepared and shared with potential participants, detailing the study's nature and purpose. During the interviews, the researcher demonstrated respect for participants by valuing their cultural backgrounds, lifestyles, and voluntary involvement. Participants were treated with respect and their significance was recognized beyond the research context. Additionally, explicit permission was obtained to record the interviews, and participants were informed of their right to access the study's results, ensuring transparency and respect for their participation.

Beneficence is a core ethical principle in research that refers to the responsibility of researchers to protect the welfare of participants by ensuring their safety and well-being. This principle is rooted in the commitment to "do no harm," which means that researchers must avoid causing physical, psychological, or emotional harm to participants. Beyond just avoiding harm, beneficence also requires researchers to actively contribute to the welfare of participants by maximizing potential benefits and minimizing any potential risks or harm associated with the research (Farrugia, 2019).

Results and Discussion

The results of the study were included in this chapter, as well as a discussion of each set of findings. It also included the researcher's study implications and synthesis based on the themes that emerged during the data analysis. There were two cases under investigation, each with a participant and informant. The researcher interviewed the participants, and the results were analyzed, and the themes were cross-checked to strengthen the study's finding in chapter 6.

Table 1. *Experiences of Elementary Teachers in Handling Reading Challenges*

<i>Emerging Themes</i>	<i>Supporting Statements</i>
Difficulty in Extending Assistance Due to Students' Habitual Absences	<p>"Attendance is a significant challenge during reading sessions. Despite my efforts to encourage consistent attendance, some students are not present. Even though I try to schedule their reading times to avoid absences, there are children who are hesitant to participate, possibly due to fear. Therefore, I see it as one of the challenges." - IDI-01</p> <p>"It seems like all of the teachers in the school face this challenge, those students who are frequently absent and will only show up during feeding programs, and will disappear afterwards. Some students as well are hesitant to return because they are afraid of reading. So, the main issue is absenteeism." - IDI-02</p> <p>"The common is absences and students with learning disabilities. Those are the common challenges that I encountered in teaching reading to my students." - IDI-03</p> <p>"I observed that the challenge Ma'am A encountered is when a student is absent or has a learning difficulty that has not been properly assessed. Since we do not have a Special Education (SPED) section or class, these students are mainstreamed into the regular classes. These students are the ones who are frequently absent and those with learning difficulties." - IDI-04</p>
Struggling to Balance the Teachers' Teaching with Other Workloads	<p>"Okay, the challenging experiences I have encountered in designing strategies to best support my students with reading difficulties I am not only focusing on the reading intervention or assisting students with reading but also dealing with various reports that needed to be submitted. This becomes one of the most challenging experiences as it hinders the ability to solely focus on teaching reading to the students. Due to paperwork and other obligations, it becomes a complex task to handle at school." - IDI-01</p> <p>"As I have mentioned, there are additional tasks such as reports, coordinatorship, and other things to give to the teacher. Instead of just merely teaching reading to your students and helping them, your time is divided because you also have to make reports to meet the submission deadlines." - IDI-02</p> <p>"One of my most difficult experiences in planning my strategies is, first the most important one is time management, because we teachers are not just, well this is realistically speaking, merely teaching reading we also have lots of reports to comply every now and then and of course prepare lessons in line with the curriculum." - IDI-03</p> <p>"I think all teachers can relate to this because we are often bombarded with teaching-related reports and tasks, so it's time management. I also observe that, at times, it can be a challenge for Ma'am A due to time constraints, especially when there are reports that needed to be done quickly." - IDI-04</p>
Challenges in Managing and	<p>"For me, based on my experience in teaching students facing reading challenges, there is a diversity in the sense that there are students or learners who quickly grasp the lessons, while others take more time. This is especially noticeable</p>

Addressing Students' Needs	<p>in far-flung areas; we are aware and also observe that due to their poverty and lack of food becomes a significant factor. As a result, their retention of lessons may be quicker, making them easily forgetful. This is something we often notice in our school.” - IDI-01</p> <p>“Each child or student is unique, so there is indeed a great diversity. Different techniques should be used to grasp the understanding of the child, and this is one of the most challenging aspects—the diversity in the way children learn. Yes, because every teacher will have different strategies and techniques depending on where the child easily learns.” - IDI-02</p> <p>“The experience for me requires patience and dedication as teachers work closely with students providing ongoing support to build their confidence and of course their literacy skills.” - IDI-03</p> <p>“She is very patient and dedicated. Patient because every day, it is not easy to teach reading, especially when she is in a higher grade where the students are expected to already know it, but since that is really the problem. Ma’am A is also very dedicated because despite the numerous tasks a teacher has to handle in a day, she consistently includes reading practice.” - IDI-04</p>
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To begin with, the first theme in the study revealed that elementary teachers had difficulty in extending assistance due to student’s habitual absences. All of the participants across the cases admitted that one of the challenges they usually encountered was student’s absences which made it difficult for them to provide the necessary assistance to help their students overcome their reading challenges effectively.

Struggling to Balance the Teachers’ Teaching with other Workloads

In related study, Perkasa et. al. (2023) stated that a teacher’s success can be judged by how well the resulting performance is. That every teacher has a teaching workload that must be passed in teaching and learning activities to meet teaching performance. Workloads are in the form of activities that must be completed within a certain time frame. When teachers are burdened with excessive administrative tasks, they may have less time and energy to devote to instructional preparation, and individualized student support. This can lead to reduced opportunities for creative and engaging teaching strategies, and limited availability for providing timely feedback and support to students.

The last theme that emerged is the challenges in managing and addressing students’ needs. This highlighted the fundamental aspect of education that educators face on a daily basis. Students come from diverse backgrounds and have varying academic abilities. Additionally, teachers must cater to the individual learning styles and preferences of each student while also addressing any academic or behavioral challenges they may face.

Additionally, the study reinforced the assertion stated by Chew and Cerbin (2021) that teachers encounter various challenges, such as accommodating different learning styles, managing classroom dynamics, and addressing specific reading difficulties, all of which require a deep understanding of their students' unique contexts. The findings emphasize that strategies effective in one classroom may not translate well to another due to differences in student backgrounds, subject matter, or educational settings. Consequently, teachers are urged to remain adaptable and responsive, continuously refining their approaches to meet the varied needs of their students. This intricate interplay of factors underscores the necessity for educators to develop a nuanced perspective and employ tailored strategies, ensuring they can effectively support and enhance learning for all students.

Table 2. *Coping Mechanisms of Elementary Teachers in Handling Reading Challenges*

<i>Emerging Themes</i>	<i>Supporting Statements</i>
Allocating Time Schedule	<p>“First, I will conduct assessments to identify the needs of each student, determining where they struggle in reading. Once I have gathered this data, I create a schedule for effective time management, prioritizing those students who require more attention in terms of their studies and schooling compared to those who can manage on their own. I focus on assessing the needs of each student and then proceed to scheduling.” - IDI-01</p> <p>“Most of the time, she allocates more extended hours for those non-readers to catch up and address what they lack because, of course, if you are a non-reader, you'll be left behind. So, gradually, extending the time allows them to gain progress slowly and catch up with the proficient readers. Extending time for reading is indeed one of her best practices.” - IDI-02</p> <p>“Prioritization begins with assessing each students’ individual needs, identifying those who require more attention and creating a flexible schedule that allocate dedicated time for targeted intervention. Also, small group instruction where I work closely with students facing reading difficulties can be scheduled during specific time blocks.” - IDI-03</p> <p>“Since the department has implemented a structured program, the reading strategies or reading practice should begin with an assessment. This is what Ma’am A did, conducting assessments and then allocating schedules. The assessment helps identify who needs more practice and who requires more individualized teaching strategies. The schedule allocation follows the assessment.” - IDI-04</p>
Making Collaboration and Taking Support from Colleagues	<p>“In our school, of course, with my colleagues, though it is easier for us to approach parents there, however in the far-flung areas, not all parents are literate enough. In those areas, some parents still do not know how to read, so I often seek help, and asked for assistance from my colleagues. We share experiences and we follow that.” - IDI-01</p> <p>“Okay, maybe the first thing to do is to ask colleagues. They say that work becomes easier when there are many people, a lot of helping hands, so, of course, we turn to our colleagues first for that. Sharing ideas, strategies, that's</p>

Using of Contextualized Materials and Individualized Instruction

where it all begins with colleagues. Specially in remote areas where we can't talk to parents, we really go straight to our colleagues.” - IDI-02 “I used to collaborate with my colleagues when it come to that kind of challenges, and also consulting my student’s parents can be valuable sources of support as well.” - IDI- 03
 “So just like any other teachers, we asked help from our colleagues, but for other practices also we asked help and support from the parents as our home learning partners.” - IDI-04
 “In our school, we only utilize the available resources and tools to support the students, especially in the school situated in far-flung areas. Before, we couldn't automatically provide reading materials that could be printed due to the absence of electricity. However, now the situation has gradually improved. As time goes by, we have coped up, thanks to the assistance of the Department of Education. They have facilitated the provision of electricity, provided printers as well sponsored resources from province. However, in my opinion, there is still a difference when comparing it to the urban areas. Here, materials are more easily accessible, especially for activities like film viewing or those related to reading, as there are various facilities, gadgets, and flat-screen TVs, which are lacking in our far-flung areas.” - IDI-01
 “As I mentioned, we really made good use of contextualized materials. Contextualized materials are especially beneficial for students in the IP community because they are more familiar and can understand better. Another factor is that they can understand more with the multitude of materials we used. According to Ma'am V, as the years go by, our reading materials also level up. But if we compare it to the city or urban areas, we may still be a bit behind, but at least teachers are doing their best to keep up with these multimedia tools that we can show to our children in far-flung areas.” - IDI-02
 “I usually do a personalized strategies such as individualized reading plans and incorporating diverse learning materials, and I also provide additional support through one-on-one sessions and fosters a supportive classroom environment that encourages confidence and engagement in reading.” - IDI-03
 “As I have observed, Ma'am A is really into individualized teaching and personalized reading plans. This is because, as I mentioned earlier, she emphasizes equity rather than equality. It depends on one-on-one sessions, focusing more on those who need it the most.” - IDI-04

Coping Mechanisms of Elementary Teachers in Handling Reading Challenges. In this point, the researcher asked the participants about their challenges they had faced as a returning student and how they cope with it. By their responses, the researcher constructed three major themes. These themes were allocating time schedule, making collaboration and taking support from colleagues, and using of contextualized materials and individualized instruction.

Table 3. *Insights of Elementary Teachers in Handling Reading Challenges*

<i>Emerging Themes</i>	<i>Supporting Statements</i>
The Contribution of Having Parental Involvement	“For me, the recommendations I can give to the parents. They should actively attend parent-teacher conferences to be aware of their child's performance in terms of reading. I also recommend to parents that they shouldn't disregard the importance of their involvement, starting from home. They should show support for their child and maintain constant communication with us teachers regarding their child. They can communicate with us anytime and attend parent-teacher conferences.” -IDI-01 “Let us start with parents, so for parents, they should attend parent-teacher conferences for them to know the standing of their children because during that time, you can discuss your child's performance, not just in reading but also in behavior, attendance, and everything. So, encourage them that they should go to school so that there is something to learn. Time passes quickly, and if we don't attend school, what will happen to us? There should be motivation coming from parents.” - IDI-02 “For parents, fostering a supportive home environment is crucial. Encourage a love for reading by providing diverse reading materials and dedicating time for shared reading experiences. Regular communication with teachers allows for collaborative efforts in addressing reading challenges. And of course, attend parent-teacher conferences and actively engage in discussions about your child's progress and specific needs.” - IDI-03 “Let us deal first with the parents. I believe that Ma'am A would recommend regular communication because parents, as our home learning partners, play a crucial role in supporting students' learning.” - IDI-04
The Importance of Adapting Various Teaching Strategies to Address Diversity	“For me, as a teacher, my insights in collecting or searching for approaches or strategies that suit or effectively address the learning needs of children in terms of reading are crucial. We need to be open-minded as teachers, not just sticking to a single approach or strategy, but applying different approaches based on the diversity of learning styles. We must identify the best strategies or approaches that suit each child, considering their understanding and pace, as there are children who comprehend quickly and others who take time, depending on our approach.” - IDI-01 “Okay, data interpretation or data analysis—of course, if you have reading materials, you certainly have data to base your conclusion on whether your student is really learning. Data interpretation involves feedback from colleagues based on their observations and feedback from the school head after observing your classroom. Classroom observation is crucial. After that, the school head provides feedback on your approach to teaching, how students read and answer questions, and it may be recognized as effective because your students can read. The effectiveness can also be tested based on the result of your data.” - IDI-02 “I often realized the dynamic nature of addressing reading challenges among my students. Through my experiences in dealing with diverse learners, I come to understand the importance of flexibility and adaptability in the instructional... in my instructional approaches. I recognize that each student's journey with reading difficulty is unique, requiring personalized strategies and

The Value of Doing Self- Reflection and Monitoring

of course an ongoing assessment.” - IDI-03

“So, I think Ma'am A has experienced that learners are very diverse and require different approaches. That's why she is very flexible and adaptive with the instructional approaches she employs for her students.” - IDI-04

“In my interaction with students, especially in reading, I reflect on my own practices to effectively support them in overcoming their reading challenges. Regularly assessing their performance helps me evaluate the effectiveness of the approaches or strategies I use. Additionally, classroom observations, feedback from colleagues, and consultations with teachers who handled the students in previous grades provide valuable insights into the students' strengths and weaknesses. It's crucial to take a student-centered approach, particularly in far-flung areas, considering the unique needs of the children.” - IDI-01

“Through direct interaction with diverse learners, of course, you can really see there where the strengths and weaknesses of the child lie, where they struggle and where you should provide support. Here, in terms of reading, it is like forging a path, molding them to align with what you want to achieve. It is important to assess the child; so, of course, we start with assessments to identify their strengths and areas needing improvement. In terms of reading, we specifically focus on reading assessments to determine their reading capacity. Ma'am V has also done this; she assessed her students to identify those who need additional help.” - IDI-02

“I engage in reflective practices to enhance my ability to support students in overcoming reading challenges. Regularly analyzing student performance data helps me to identify specific areas of difficulty, it also allows me to tailor my instruction to address individual needs. Classroom observations and feedback from colleagues provide valuable external perspectives, offering insights into effective teaching methods and areas for improvement. Through self-reflection, I critically assess the success of my instructional approaches, considering what worked well and what could be refined. I also solicit direct feedback from students about their learning experiences and further informs teachers about the impact of their methods of my methods, fostering a student- centered approach.” - IDI-03

“I also think that Ma'am A is constantly and consistently reflecting on her practices in teaching reading. She analyzes student performance data regularly, which informs her about areas for improvement and what to focus on as she teaches reading to her students.” - IDI-04

Allocating Time Schedule

In relation to the result, the study of Whitlock and Brugar (2019) stated that unstructured time in the school day can be academic or non-academic. Academic unstructured time is a space where the students are not directly engaged in a teacher-directed lesson, but are completing work that contributes to academic success in a specific subject area. Teachers define these experiences where students are engaging in work that is academic in a broad sense, but may not be connected to specific objectives. It was found that allocating time schedules effectively is essential for fostering student success. A well-structured and thoughtfully planned schedule ensures that students have ample opportunities to engage with learning materials, participate in meaningful activities, and receive targeted support as needed.

Making Collaboration and Taking Support from Colleagues

In relation to the study of Bharaj (2019), the study highlighted that collaboration breaks down the segmented setup of educational institutions and fosters a secure and encouraging atmosphere for educators. This enables them to exchange valuable insights concerning content or teaching methods, all with the shared goal of enhancing the learning environment for students. Collaborative efforts assist teachers in refining their instructional techniques and also play a role in boosting their job satisfaction. Through collaborative efforts, teachers have the opportunity to learn from each other, explore new teaching strategies, and receive constructive feedback on their instructional practices. This continuous exchange of ideas and experiences not only benefits individual teachers but also contributes to the collective improvement of teaching quality within the educational institution.

Using of Contextualized Materials and Individualized Instruction

The related study of Rao et. al. (2023) and Ishartiwi et. al. (2023) emphasized that in education, contextualization links learning material to students' experiences and background knowledge, rendering it both relevant and meaningful. This approach situates content within real- world contexts, demonstrating the practical applications and significance of the concepts being taught. Conversely, individualized instruction methods exhibit variability based on teachers' perspectives. Despite the need to tailor instruction to meet each student's needs, this approach consistently yields positive outcomes in skill acquisition.

Insights of Elementary Teachers in Handling Reading Challenges. After retrieving and

analyzing the data gathered from the participants, it was revealed that the elementary teachers have various insights in terms of dealing students with reading challenges. The researcher identified three themes which were the contribution of having parental involvement, the importance of adapting various teaching strategies to address diversity, and the value of doing self-reflection and monitoring.

Contribution of Having Parental Pnvovement

In line with this, the study of Skreekanth (2023) found that parents perceive their high level of involvement as primarily aimed at improving their children's quality of life. The greater the level of involvement, the more likely it is for the child to succeed in education, as parents go above and beyond to ensure their children's well-being, which positively impacts their education. Parents who consistently

demonstrate high levels of involvement are deeply committed to their children's education, and this dedication can have a positive influence on their children's progress and academic performance. Parents who are highly involved in their children's education not only prioritize academic success but also actively contribute to fostering a supportive and enriching learning environment at home and in the community. Their unwavering support and encouragement serve as powerful motivators for children, reinforcing the importance of education and instilling a strong sense of academic responsibility.

The Importance of Adapting Various Teaching Strategies to Address Diversity

In accordance to the study of Bhat et. al. (2021), it was demonstrated that learning styles can be successfully accommodated in each session through careful planning and the implementation of active learning techniques. This dynamic approach in the classroom has led to the attainment of the desired goals. The study concludes that addressing learning diversity is only possible when teachers are knowledgeable about learning styles and employ active learning strategies effectively. By embracing dynamic classroom strategies, educators foster an inclusive learning environment where every student feels valued and supported in their academic journey. It allows educators to create inclusive and supportive learning environments where every student has the opportunity to thrive academically and personally.

The Value of Doing Self-reflection and Monitoring

In the study of Chacón (2018) highlighted the necessity for implementing alternative teaching methods that prompt teachers and teacher educators to engage in reflective practices. Advocates of reflective teaching argue that meaningful change can only occur when educators actively reflect on their practice both during and after teaching sessions. This reflective process allows teachers to draw insights from their experiences, confront the uncertainties inherent in everyday classroom situations, and adapt their instructional approaches to meet the diverse needs of their students within the broader sociocultural context. By embracing reflection-in-action and reflection-on-action, educators can not only inform their teaching practices but also generate new knowledge and enhance their capacity to effectively support student learning and development.

Conclusions

This multiple case study underscores the complexities of supporting elementary students with reading challenges, highlighting the need for a multifaceted approach that considers individual needs, effective instructional practices, and collaborative partnerships. Teachers' insights emphasize the importance of ongoing professional development, access to diverse resources, and a supportive school environment to effectively address these challenges. Future research should explore the long-term impact of various interventions on student reading development, providing valuable data to inform evidence-based practices and improve literacy outcomes for all elementary learners.

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